

**IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL MILITARY AGREEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF
NIGERIA-RUSSIA MILITARY COOPERATION**

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ABSTRACT

The problem of banditry in Nigeria has raised so much dust in the country's political terrain partly due to the inability of the Nigeria Armed Forces to uphold their statutory role of maintaining the country's territorial integrity and to protect it against external attacks. The effects are continuous decline in the economy of the country, exponential rise in unemployment curve, food crises and hunger. Hence, several modalities were put in place by the government which yield no positive result. Worse comes to worse when the U.S government agreed to assist by providing them with the necessary weapons and training their Armed Forces. The study investigated the issues of violation of human rights, siphoning of military hardwares to unscrupulous individuals which prompted the U.S government to suspend further military assistance and cooperation with Nigeria. Awaken by the irresistible cry for help, Moscow availed to undertake a military and technical agreement with Abuja. The study recommends such agreement as timely and must be implemented beyond mere political rethorics. Implementation of the Nigeria-Russian military agreement will further promote and strengthen bilateral relations between Moscow and Abuja.

Keywords: Military Cooperation, Armed forces, Foreign policy

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INTRODUCTION

Sequel to the 1884–1885 Berlin Conference on Africa, the major European powers scrambled not only for prestige but also for dominance in Africa for the purpose of political and economic gains. Although the imperial Russia was at the conference but never a party to the balkanization of Africa during the Soviet era, its activities were centred on and joined with the Africans on their tortuous way to independence owing to its policy of equality and peaceful coexistence among all the peoples of the world. Moscow remains the only major power that has never colonized any country in Africa. Instead, it was active especially in giving impetus to the anti-colonial struggles. The Kremlin's moral and political repudiation of colonial domination was an essential catalyst to the eventual collapse of formal colonialism in Nigeria and in Africa at large. The initial principle of Russia's foreign policy toward Africa owed much to the view of V.I Lenin – equality and peace among all people of the world. just like the biblical message of Moses to the Egyptian Pharaoh: "let my people go". It was this same message that Khrushchev (the former Soviet leader) took to the plenary meeting of the XVth session of the United Nations General assembly with a motion to end all forms of colonization by 1960. The passage of the motion led to the crumbling of colonialism, and sovereign African states began to emerge one after another and Nigeria took its turn to gain independence in 1960, a year that is generally noted as "Africa's year"]. Being a superpower in the atmosphere of the "cold war", the Soviet Union pursued such policy that would create its image of a champion for national liberation and make Africa's presence on the international arena conspicuous, clearly noticed and appreciated. The Soviet Union policy makers built into its foreign policy architecture a sensitive and positive response to assist Africa in building an egalitarian society for themselves. This came in form of aids and provision of infrastructural amenities. One can mention the Answan dam in Egypt, hydro energy plants in Guinea, Zambia, Mali and Madagascar, Ajaokuta steel rolling mills in Nigeria and other projects in various parts of Africa. The immediate recognition of Nigeria's sovereignty and independence, assistance to prevent the disintegration of Nigeria during the civil war (1967–1970) and the education of the Nigerians who had been deliberately kept untrained and

uneducated by their colonialists marked the starting point from where the relations between Nigeria and Russia grew. But little or no effort has been made to boost Nigeria military strength as per its statutory role of maintaining territorial integrity of the country. Unfortunately, Nigeria military has been rated poorly due to her inability to perform her statutory role due to the daring influences of terrorism and banditry in some parts of the country.

The Military as an Institution

As an institution the military has many justifications for seeking a political role. Four important reasons are discussed below. First of all, the military wants to maintain an increase in the military's share of national resources. Case studies often note that one reason for a military take over a rise in military expenditures is evidenced, such as a rise in salaries, new military hardware are ordered, and new facilities are provided to the officers and their families. For instance, military expenditures rose by an average of 22% per year in Ghana over the period 1966-69, following a military coup against Nkrumah's government (Anton Bebler, 1973). This is in fact a reflection of the fact that prior to the coup Nkrumah had placed the army on an austerity budget. A second reason for the role of military in politics is simply the maintenance and survival of the armed forces within a country and this is often seen when attempts are made to undermine military hierarchy. For example, in the case of Brazil, President Goulart tried to counter the power of top military officers and consequently was overthrown by the military in April 1964 (Eric A Nordlinger, 1977). The military also gets involved in political power if a politician, who was removed by the military in past, becomes active again. For example, it is one of the key reasons for the coups in Ecuador and Guatemala during 1963 (Martin Needler, 1964; Nordlinger, 1977). A third reason for military involvement in politics is fear of national disintegration. For example, military officers often argue that their intervention in politics is necessary because civilian governments are inefficient, corrupt and incapable of governing a country and as a result the country is plagued by widespread political, economic and social disorders. In fact, a military intervention or

take over becomes easy in the presence of weak, poorly elected civilian-dominated governments.

These governments often fail to respond to the voices and needs of a large segment of society. As a result, military-dominated governments are initially welcomed because they promise to curb corruption and to respond to the needs of the poor people. However, in practice military governments do not follow through on these pledges. The evidence shows that the military dominated governments appear as inefficient and corrupt as their civilian predecessors. A fourth reason for military involvement is the extension of the concept of 'national security' to include internal securities. Militaries not only devise military techniques and doctrine for confronting domestic insurgency but they are also interested in the social and political reasons for insurgency. In countries where civilian-dominated governments are more unrepresentative, the military comes to power in an attempt to institutionalize their role, such as in Indonesia, Chile and Brazil. At present, most developing world militaries are mainly concerned with internal security that implies in future military officers throughout the world will be more interested in politics and government. Transparency International (TI) (2017) informed the Nigerian armed forces that corruption in the military is dangerous, divisive, wasteful and fuels insurgency. It said where graft is entrenched among military establishment, was dangerous. This was made known at a one-day Leadership Workshop organised by the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) in conjunction with Transparency International and the Civil Society Legislative Advocacy Centre (CSLAC). Senior Advisor to TI, Ian Andrews, explained that high level of corruption in the military has the tendency to derail national growth, development and even stir up insurgencies and warfare. He maintained that the problem of corruption in military establishments across the globe, adding that corruption in military procurement was not peculiar to Nigeria, but a global challenge which undermines confidence in state institutions. He said: "Corruption in military establishment is dangerous, divisive and wasteful with far reaching consequences on the state, and fuels insurgency". As Dixon, et.al (2017:2) rightly observed that corruption has been particularly destructive in the Defense and security sector. Overlooked in

peacetime, Defense sector corruption has devastating real world consequences when conflict flares. With lower oil prices, corrupt elites have increasingly exploited alternative illicit revenue streams. The secret nature of Defense and security budgets has made them the easiest and most lucrative opportunity to exploit. While Boko Haram has constructed a conflict economy geared around pillage, racketeering, and kidnapping; senior players in the Nigerian security sector have also profited from the insurgency.

DEFENCE INDUSTRIES CORPORATION OF NIGERIA

HISTORY:

The Defence Industries Corporation of Nigeria was established by an Act of Parliament in 1964. Consequently a West German manufacturing firm Fritz Werner was assigned the task of providing technical expertise and set up the Ordnance Factory in Kaduna.

The first Technical Partner of the Defence Industries Corporation of Nigeria (DICON) was Fritz Werner of Western Germany. FW designed and built the Kaduna Ordnance Factories in 1964 with the following production capacities, 5000 units of BM 59 Rifles per annum, 18,000 units of SMG 12 per annum, 12,000,000 rounds of 7.62mm x 51 per annum and 4,000,000 rounds of 9mm x 19 per annum.

The Nigerian Civil War which occurred between 1967 -1970 necessitated the tripling of the above production rates and the factory was thus able to make a significant contribution to the war effort. After the war in 1970, the lucrative arms market for DICON ended. Therefore, in order to remain in business DICON decided to use its equipment to produce civilian items like rural water supply equipment, industrial spare parts and furniture for sale to the public.

MISSION OF DICON

To operate the ordinance factories for the manufacture and supply of arms and ammunition as well as inspecting, testing and recommending ordinance material intended for use by the Armed Forces and other security organizations while using the excess capacity to support the development of local Industries.

VISION OF DICON

A Corporation built on a sound Commercial footing to continuously produce and constantly improve on the quality of arms and ammunition needs of the Defence, Security and foreign policy of Nigeria with the best international standards.

(defence.gov.ng)

Corporation is the art or practice of conducting international relations. The role of military corporation manifests itself in its two basic components: preventive corporation and coercive corporation. Within the framework of preventive corporation, the military component is aimed to achieve the climate of confidence, necessary for the improvement of relations between two nations. This can be called peacetime military corporation. The best approach to the prevention of confrontation between two countries is to identify of common interests and to widen cooperation between them in diverse fields, particularly `military'. Depending upon the nature of relations between the states, the interests, peacetime military corporation has to find the best rhythm for the development of military relations.

Nigeria's Foreign Policy

An overview of Nigeria's foreign policy from gaining independence until now has received the attention of scholars, career diplomats and top government functionaries. The policy is generally observed as put together by Ignatius Ollisemeka (2008), the former Nigerian External Affairs Minister, that Africa has always been the centrepiece of the Nigerian foreign policy, and this policy has been consistent and continuous. Victor Chibundu [6, p. 6] also remarked that the emphasis, style and implementation of the policy for many reasons have varied from one government to another. Both of them, however, agreed that the essentials and fundamentals of Nigeria's foreign policy have remained steadfast. All these are attributable to the foundation laid by the architects of Nigeria's foreign policy during the first republic. Among them are the following: Jaja Anucha Wachukwu (Nigeria's first Foreign Minister), Sir Abubarkar Tafawa Balewa (Prime Minister of Nigeria 1960–1966) and Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe (Nigeria's first President). Nigeria's foreign policy evolved from the ideas put together by its early political, intellectual and foreign affairs experts. Their intention is to project Nigeria to play a major role in world affairs in general and Africa in particular.

The social factors, economic demands, religious affinities, security needs and dimensions of global politics have reshaped Nigeria's view on foreign relations which made it establish contacts and form allies with other nations beyond the borders of Africa among which Russia is prominent.

Peacetime Military Cooperation

Peacetime military cooperation is an important constituent of the five basic channels of nation-to-nation contact between friendly governments, i.e., political, diplomatic, economic, cultural/social, and last but not the least, military. As a component of foreign policy, it aims to bring in greater transparency and confidence in the military sphere and contribute towards closer relations with countries through constructive use of defence resources in times of peace. It also serves as a means of conveying a nation's security concerns and perceptions and creation of a favourable security environment.

While it is true that cooperation is the first line of defence and defence is the last, it can be reasoned that in between, one can have military cooperation, whereby the military is seen as an additional channel and avenue by which conflicts could be averted, if not resolved. Rather than viewing military cooperation and force as opposing ends of the spectrum of national policy where one is used when the other fails it is important to recognise that each must seamlessly support the other. This entails striking the right balance between foreign policy and security interests and strengthening military relations through foreign policy tools like military training programmes, arms transfers, security dialogues and confidence-building measures. These efforts pay off, with stronger security relationships with other countries. Military cooperation does not in any way develop outside the cooperation between states and the scope and scale of military relations are influenced by the tenor of overall relations. The government spells out the broad parameters of foreign policy and military cooperation is an essential component of this policy.

India has an abiding stake in peace and stability in its neighbourhood for its long-term security and projection on the regional and eventually the world scene. One of the objectives of India's foreign policy is the intensification and consolidation of ties with the neighbours and strengthening of peace and security in the region as a whole,

through mutually beneficial cooperation. Peacetime military corporation can help to build the foundation for regional cooperation, which is based on mutual trust and confidence. Upgrading military ties, by looking at various alternatives of peacetime military corporation in a sustained manner, can reduce the security concerns in the region and assist in the fulfilment of the foreign policy objectives. International Military Training Cooperation (IMTC) is an essential component of peacetime military corporation and can prove vital in furthering India's strategic interests.

Indian Military Training Cooperation

The Indian Armed Forces have the experience of operating over varied terrain, which is possibly unique in the world. The Indian Army has some of the finest training facilities in jungle, snow and desert warfare. The operational deployment and sustainability range from mountains and glaciers in the North, to the deserts of Rajasthan, and from the jungles of the North-East to the marine environment of the Island territories. They have continuing operational experience in the entire spectrum of conflict, from operations other than war, to low-intensity conflict and conventional war fighting. 25 The forces have a rich tradition of highly professional training, supported by state-of-the-art training facilities, constantly updated and refined through live combat experience. The vast expertise can therefore be utilised to impart meaningful training to the defence forces of countries in the regions of interest, as also to conduct joint training, to build up close military ties and healthy, mutually beneficial bilateral relations. Military training cooperation can therefore be made a focal point of India's peacetime military diplomacy.

It is however necessary to draw out essential parameters within which IMTC will need to be used by India. A careful cost-benefit security/strategic analysis will have to be done prior to providing training assistance to specific countries, as resources are scarce. For this be the countries are to be prioritised, in consultations with the MEA, for developing, maintaining and fostering military training cooperation. Protecting sensitive

technologies and information will be of prime importance during joint training and exercises. It will also be imperative to ensure safety of own troops provided as part of training teams with other countries.

Training Courses with Foreign Armed Forces

Professional courses with foreign armed forces, especially advanced countries like the US, offer an excellent opportunity to acquire specialised skills for any country for its armed forces which would help in enhancing their own training standards. Participation in such courses also enables the participants to interact with counterparts from other countries and build long-term relationships, which can be beneficial to all the participating services. So, it is essential to avail of courses being offered by other countries, irrespective of the size and status of the country offering the course, to have a more visible presence at different levels in the foreign military training establishments. This will also help to establish long lasting ties, with future military leaders of the countries in the areas of interest. It is for this reason that India sends officers to attend courses in smaller countries like Bangladesh. India welcomed the Chinese invitation to send officers to attend courses at the National Defence University in Beijing. Three officers one each from the Army, Navy and the Air Force are attending a one-year course there, which began in September 2002. It will be in India's interest if more officers are sent to attend professional courses in the training institutions of the PLA.

Training Courses in India

Military training is India's forte and it is essential to take advantage of this strength to harness the goodwill of the younger military generation of other countries in the regions of interest and to establish strategic relationship with them. Towards this end, India is imparting military training to the personnel of friendly foreign countries, under the Indian

Technical and Economic Cooperation (ITEC) and Special Aid Programmes (for Bhutan and Sri Lanka) of the MEA, Special Aid Programme (for Nepal) of the Ministry of Defence and under bilateral reciprocal schemes. During 2002-03, as many as 128 foreign military personnel were trained under ITEC through long and short-term courses in the training institutions of the three services.

The MEA allocates funds for training of foreign military personnel of many countries, and course allocation in the training institutions of the three services is based on availability of this fund. But, is not adequate for the desired level of military-to-military cooperation and needs to be substantially enhanced. India should aim to have military officers of nearly all South-Asian countries in its training courses, even if it means doubling the intake into some of the courses. Training assistance provided to countries in South-East Asia should also be vastly increased. This would lead to greater reliance of these countries on India for specialised training and reduction of the influence and hold of countries like China. Till the time India's National Defence University is set up, personnel from Chinese Armed Forces can be offered courses at the Indian National Defence College at New Delhi and Defence Services Staff College at Wellington.

India needs to utilise the expertise gained in UN peacekeeping operations by imparting training to other countries in various facets of peacekeeping. A large pool of personnel who have participated in these operations, are available as instructors. Their experience and feedback after each mission helps in updating the training content and methodologies at the Peacekeeping Training Centre in Delhi. With the proven de-mining capability and vast experience in dealing with Improvised Explosive Devices and disposal of unexploded ordinance, the Indian Army can impart practical training to the personnel of friendly countries.

The former Soviet Union/Russia has been the major supplier of defence equipment to India and India has always been the model for developing countries in maximising the utility of the Soviet designed weapons and technology that the designers in turn, further improved them. Over a period of time, India has built up the necessary infrastructure

and expertise to handle this equipment and also service it. It can therefore, offer to train the crew and technicians of countries in the region who are holding Soviet or Russian equipment (The training of Malaysian MIG aircraft pilots and ground support staff by India is a suitable example in this context).

The training requirements of the Indian Navy are varied and multi-dimensional. This has necessitated the establishment of a number of basic and specialised training academies and institutions throughout the country. It would be beneficial to train foreign naval personnel in specialised areas such as submarine warfare and helicopter operations. The hydrographic capability of the Indian Navy is today the fourth largest in the world. The Indian Naval Hydrographic Department possesses vast experience with a longstanding tradition of professionalism, state-of-the-art equipment, modern infrastructure and trained personnel. The Indian Naval Hydrographic Centre can organise and conduct training programmes on a regular basis for naval officers of the Indian Ocean littoral countries. This would enable those countries to establish hydrographic departments for their navies if they do not have them already, and also participate in the survey large areas of the seabed in a joint and coordinated manner.

The aspect of English language training, before imparting professional training to students of those countries where of English is not commonly used, has to be taken into account. It is advantageous to have the training syllabus for officers in the services in English language as it is used in several countries. It may be desirable to design courses wherein English language and IT application are first imparted first, followed by the requisite training in the appropriate fields/specialisation at the training institutes in India.

Workshops/Seminars/Conferences

A number of countries regularly hold important workshops/seminars/ conferences on regional security and current issues of importance. Participation in these seminars exposes the participants to the perspectives of various participating nations, on the existing security environment and current trends. Such events can facilitate interaction among regional militaries and serve as non-political fora for senior military officers to meet and discuss professional military subjects on a non-attribution basis. They also provide opportunities to voice opinions and make others see India's viewpoint, on important global and regional issues. The College of Defence Management, Secunderabad invited for the first time, representatives from friendly countries to attend its annual seminar in January 2003 with the focus on 'National Security'. India needs to become the regional hub for strategic thinking thought and organise defence seminars on a regular basis, inviting service officers from the world over.

Indian Military Training Teams in Other Countries

India has been sending training teams to a number of developing countries to impart military training to their personnel and has also cooperated with these countries to assist them in establishing training institutions on the Indian model. India has very strong ties with Africa. After independence it became the voice of the colonised countries and showed the way in the opposition to Apartheid. It has also been training the armed forces of a number of African countries. It now finds Africa a source for its growing oil and gas needs and so increased cooperation will be still more important. In addition, efforts India needs to make to locate our training teams in the neighbouring countries like Myanmar, Nepal, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka to decrease their dependence on countries like China and the US.

Joint Training Exercises

Combined exercises between defence forces facilitate inter-operability and conduct of joint military operations against a common threat. They provide insight into each other's leadership techniques, battle drills and standard operating procedures. By training together in peacetime, confusion and delays are prevented and joint operations made smooth and effective. Confidence levels, professional trust and respect are built up through joint exercises. Moreover, such exercises convey signals to potential adversaries and challengers of authority, about the joint military response their actions could invite.

Nigeria-Russia Military Agreement

In accordance to the vision of the Defense Cooperation of Nigeria, the best approach to the prevention of confrontation between two countries is to identify of common interests and to widen cooperation between them in diverse fields, particularly `military'. Depending upon the nature of relations between the states, the interests, peacetime military corporation has to find the best rhythm for the development of military relations. Hence, Nigerian Embassy in Moscow announced in 2021 the signing of a legal framework agreement that would provide for Russia to supply Nigeria with military equipment and training. The Agreement on Military-Technical Cooperation also provides for "after-sales services, training of personnel in respective educational establishments, and technology transfer."

In 2019, Nigerian President Muhammadu Buhari reportedly raised the possibility of such an agreement with Russian President Vladimir Putin which was effected in 2021.

Media sees the agreement as related to U.S. congressional hesitancy to authorize the sale to Nigeria of certain military equipment because of human rights concerns. Indeed, Nigerian desire to buy such materiel—and American reluctance to sell, often on human rights grounds—is a perennial irritant to the bilateral relationship. Nigeria already uses military equipment from Russia and other military suppliers as well as the United States.

The just-signed agreement is a legal framework only; Nigeria has not entered into a new agreement actually to make new purchases. With respect to Nigeria, Russia is likely to be “transactional”—can its companies make money? Any accompanying increase in political influence Moscow will regard as a secondary dividend.

Problems of Nigeria-Russia Relations

There are several challenges confronting Nigeria-Russia relations. For instance, in order for agreements among nations to become operational, they are to be passed by the National parliament and that forms their legal framework. The agreements signed with Russia are yet to be ratified by the parliament with particular reference to the Abuja agreement of 2009.

Adequate knowledge and clear understanding of culture, history, language, mentality, world-view, capabilities and potentials of other nations are crucial to foreign policy. It facilitates correct and accurate perception on which policies on diplomacy rests.

There is weak indication that the two countries have sufficient and adequate perception of each other. This in part is responsible for the lack of the political will to fully implement their existing bilateral agreements. The other problems of Nigeria – Russia are as follows:

* Political orientation. The majority among the Nigeria political elites are under strong influence of London and Washington whose interest is to distance Moscow from the affairs of African countries.

* U.S banned Nigeria. U.S lawmakers put a hold on a proposal to sell almost \$1 billion worth of weapons to Nigeria over concerns about possible human rights abuses by the government.

* Trade imbalance. There should be created more adequate environment for Nigeria to increase its export to Russia. Tropical agricultural products like cashew, coffee, and cocoa can be sourced from Nigeria by Russian industries.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The common features which Russia and Nigeria exhibit are more compelling than politics and economy, population size or natural endowments. Afons Adebisi (2010) mirrored quite a number of similarities in the culture of these two nations, which, in our view, if well explored should enhance their relationship. Particular attention was drawn to some of their traditions, mentality and way of life. For example, traditionally, Russians worshipped water which is a reflection of Osun Oshogbo – (god of water) in Nigeria, also, worship of iron in Russia is similar to Ogun (god of iron) in Nigeria. Of particular interest is the tradition of marriage in these two countries. Among the Yorubas in Nigeria, for example, marriage is described as: “carry the wife” (gbe iyawo.) As a sign of love, the Russians do carry their wives in their hands and sometimes walk distance before they embark on what they call ‘gulanie’ (strolling) either in a park or any historical place from where they proceed to the reception. “To carry” in this case symbolizes taking full responsibilities for her. Apart from all these, in terms of character, the Russian and the Nigerian people like making themselves noticeable

wherever they found themselves, which is always accompanied by 'some excesses' in terms of the spending habit.

In the area of governance, the tsarist era in Russia was a period of absolute power where the reign was passed from father to son. This is almost the same in the precolonial Nigeria even till date.

As noted by Agubamah, Russia has a lot to offer Nigeria in terms of technological support in several critical areas. In addition, Russia has a track record of nurturing several countries technological wise. Algeria reportedly remains the biggest recipient of Russian arms in Africa, followed by Egypt, Sudan, and Angola.

The need for Nigeria-Russian military cooperation is expedient so as to put a stop to banditry and terrorism in the country which have ravaged the country for many years. Therefore, there is urgent need for the Nigerian government to revisit the Nigeria-Russian military agreement and give passage to its legal framework as a matter of necessity to enable the arm forces keep to their statutory role of maintaining the country's territorial integrity.

CONCLUSION

The relations between nations are established to serve national interests. Nigeria-Russia relations should be focused and geared towards the promotion of the cultural heritage, scientific, economic and technical/technological cooperation. A strive to facilitate good diplomatic relations between Abuja and Moscow.

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